
The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of Teacher Job Satisfaction and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement and the effect of Teacher Job Satisfaction and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement through Classroom Discipline at UPT SPF Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

This research approach uses quantitative research. The population is teachers at UPT SPF Public Middle Schools in the Rappocini sub-district of Makassar city consisting of UPT SPF SMP Negeri 21, UPT SPF- SMP Negeri 40 and UPT SPF SMP Negeri 13 UPT SPF SMP Negeri 33, UPT SPF- SMP Negeri 48 and UPT SPF SMP Negeri 49 Makassar with a population of 320 teachers. Sampling used purposive random sampling technique, namely each subject teacher was represented by 2 subject teachers so that the number of samples was 20 SMPN 21, 20 SMPN 40 students and 20 SMPN 13 students, 20 SMPN 33 students, 10 SMPN 48 students. 10 people and SMPN 49 with a total sample of 100 teachers. This research data collection method uses: Questionnaire and Observation and Data analysis method used in this research is Path Analysis.

The results of the study showed that there was an effect of teacher job satisfaction (X1), teacher guidance (X2) and class discipline (Z) on student achievement (Y) at the UPTSPF of state junior high schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city. There is an influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) Teacher Guidance (X2) and Class Discipline (Z) simultaneously on student achievement. There is no effect of Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) on Student Learning Achievement (Y) Through Class Discipline (Z). There is no effect of Teacher Guidance (X2) on Student Achievement (Y) through Class Discipline (Z) at the UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.

KEYWORDS: Teacher Job Satisfaction, Teacher Guidance, Class Discipline and Student Achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Student Learning Achievement is the result that has been achieved from what has been done/done (Big Indonesian Dictionary, 2003: 895), whereas according to Tu'u in Aina Mulyana 2022 learning achievement is the mastery of knowledge or skills developed by the subject, usually indicated by test scores or grades given by the teacher. According to Sukmadinata (2003: 101), "Learning Achievement is the realization or expansion of the potential skills or capacities possessed by students". To achieve learning achievement, good performance from teachers is required. Teacher performance can be seen from student learning achievement. Teacher performance is influenced by teacher job satisfaction. Barnawi (2012: 135), suggests that viewing job satisfaction as the overall result of the degree of liking or disliking employees towards various aspects of the job. As stated by Sinambela (2012: 256) that performance satisfaction is a person's feelings towards his work which are produced by his own efforts (internal) and which are supported by things from outside himself (external), regarding work conditions, work results, and work itself. Apart from job satisfaction which influences learning achievement, direct and continuous teacher guidance determines the success of the learning process which results in learning achievement. Teaching according to Abin Syamsuddin (2003) states that teachers as mentors are required to be able to identify students who are suspected of experiencing difficulties in learning, carry out diagnoses and prognoses, and if it is still within the limits of their authority, must help solve them (remedial teaching). Teachers in carrying out learning as the spearhead of learning, one of the competencies that must be possessed is being able to manage the class well, such as disciplining the class, class discipline is behavior that reflects compliance with various values agreed upon by all, both students, teachers and employees as stated in the rules. school/class order According to observations, the teachers at the UPT SPF State Middle Schools in the Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City, have not developed themselves to the maximum. This can be seen in students' learning achievements which still need to be improved. This can be seen from the results of competitions in subjects which have not yet won. It is assumed that the way to guide teachers in the teaching and learning process is such as; There are still teachers when teaching or guiding who are not optimal in teaching, for example they do not use media as learning materials and the learning process seems boring so that students' learning motivation is low (2). There are still teachers

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

who, when guiding or teaching, only give assignments, then leave the students. Based on the background of the problem above, the objectives of this research are as follows: 1. To find out and analyze whether Teacher Job Satisfaction influences Learning Achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city 2. To find out and analyze whether Teacher Guidance has an effect on Learning Achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city 3. To find out and analyze whether Class Discipline influences Learning Achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city 4. To find out and analyze whether Teacher Job Satisfaction, Teacher Guidance, and Class Discipline simultaneously influence Student Learning Achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city 5. To determine and analyze the influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction on Student Learning Achievement through Class Discipline at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in the Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City 6. To determine and analyze the influence of Teacher Guidance on Student Learning Achievement through Class Discipline at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in the Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City As a follow-up to the background of the problem, it is deemed necessary to review theories related to independent variables such as job satisfaction, according to Hasibuan (2001), is an emotional attitude of being pleasant and loving one's job, whereas according to Anan (2011), job satisfaction is a set of employee feelings about being pleasant. their work or not. that the factors that determine job satisfaction are as follows: 1. Teacher relationship factors: a) direct relationship between the principal and the teacher, b) psychological factors and working conditions, c) suggestions from coworkers, d) emotions and work situations. 2. Individual factors: a) attitude, b) age, c) gender. 3. External factors: a) family conditions, b) recreation, c) education. Meanwhile, teacher guidance according to Abin Syamsuddin (2003) states that teachers as mentors are required to be able to identify students who are suspected of having learning difficulties, carry out diagnoses, prognosis, and if it is still within the limits of its authority, must help solve it

Figure 1. research conceptual framework

- H1: It is suspected that teacher job satisfaction influences student learning achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city.
- H2: It is suspected that teacher guidance has an influence on learning achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city.
- H3: It is suspected that Class Discipline has an influence on Learning Achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City
- H4: It is suspected that Teacher Job Satisfaction, Teacher Guidance, and Class Discipline simultaneously influence Student Learning Achievement at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in the Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City
- H5: It is suspected that there is an influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction on Student Learning Achievement through Class Discipline at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City
- H6: It is suspected that there is an influence of Teacher Guidance on Student Learning Achievement through Class Discipline at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is quantitative research, which is an approach used in research through mathematical calculations to scientifically prove whether there are relationships that occur between variables. The population in this study were all teachers who taught at State Middle Schools in the Rappocini sub-district, Makassar City, consisting of UPT SPF, SMP Negeri 21, UPT SPF- SMP Negeri 40 and UPT SPF, SMP Negeri 13, UPT SPF, SMP Negeri 33, UPT SPF- SMP Negeri 48. and UPT SPF SMP Negeri 49 Makassar with a population of 320 teachers. Sampling used purposive random sampling technique, namely each subject teacher was represented by 2 subject teachers so that the number of

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

samples was 20 at SMPN 21, 20 at SMPN 40 and 20 at SMPN 13, 20 at SMPN 33, 10 at SMPN 48. people and SMPN 49 as many as 10 people, the total sample is 100 teachers. The data collection method for this research uses: Questionnaires and Observations and the data analysis method used in this research is Path Analysis. According to Sulyanto 2011 path analysis is an extension of the regression model which is used to analyze the relationship between variables with the aim of finding out the direct or indirect influence of a set of independent variables on the dependent variable Structural equation of path analysis which includes X1, X2 as independent variables (exogenous variables), Z is the intervening variable, Y is the dependent variable (endogenous variable) and E= Error as follows: Where:

Model 1: $Z = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 X_2 + \epsilon_1$

Model 2: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 Z + (\alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 X_2 + \epsilon_1) + \epsilon_2$

Information:

Y = Learning Achievement X1 = Teacher Job Satisfaction X2 = Teacher Guidance

Z = Class Discipline $\alpha_0 + \beta_0$ = Coefficient

$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression Coefficients ϵ_1 = Regression Value 1

ϵ_2 = Regression Value 2

Calculation of path coefficients using SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solution) software version 15.0 through partial regression analysis where the path coefficients are standardized regression coefficients (standardized beta coefficients) for the direct effect, while the indirect effect is the multiplication of the path coefficients of the path What each equation goes through and the total effect is the sum of the direct effects and all the indirect effects.

Uji Signifikansi Hipotesis

Uji Simultan (Uji F)

Hasil Output SPSS:

Tabel 1 Uji F

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	194,179	3	64,726	19,675	,000 ^b
Residual	315,821	96	3,290		
Total	510,000	99			

Dependent Variable: Student Achievement (Y)

Predictors: (Constant), Class Discipline (Z), Teacher Guidance (X2), Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1)

In table 1. The simultaneous test shows that there is a significant influence between the independent variable (X) simultaneously on the dependent variable (Y) which can be seen in the table above, namely with the sig value. F test of 0.000 at a significance level of 0.05. This value is smaller than 0.05, which indicates that all independent variables consist of; Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1), Teacher Guidance (X2). and Class Discipline (Z) together influence Student Learning Achievement (Y). at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini sub-district, Makassar city.

Hasil Analisis Uji- t Output SPSS

Tabel 2 Uji- t

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7,163	1,704		4,204	,000
	Teacher Job Satisfaction(X1)	,421	,130	,324	3,251	,002
	Teacher Guidance (X2)	,227	,087	,258	2,595	,011
	Class Discipline (Z)	,193	,093	,184	2,079	,040

a. Dependent Variable: Student Learning Achievement (Y)

In table 2, the partial test is a test to determine the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The following conclusions can be drawn from the table above:

- 1) The probability value of X1 is 0.002. This value is smaller than 0.05 or the calculated t value is 3,125 > t table 1,984 (n-1 = 100-1 alpha 5%) so it can be concluded that the Teacher Job Satisfaction variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

on the Student Learning Achievement variable (Y) at UPT SPF for state junior high schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.

- 2) The probability value of X2 is 0.040. This value is smaller than 0.05 or the calculated t value is 2,595 > t table 1,984 (n-1 = 100-1 alpha 5%) so it can be concluded that the Teacher Guidance variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the Student Learning Achievement variable (Y) at the UPT SPF of state junior high schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.
- 3) The probability value Z is 0.026. This value is smaller than 0.05 or the calculated t value is 2,079 > t table 1.984 (n-1 = 100-1 alpha 5%) so it can be concluded that the Class Discipline variable (Z) has a positive and significant effect on the Student Learning Achievement variable (Y) at the UPT SPF of state junior high schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.

Results of Path Test Analysis and Sobel Test Results of Model I path regression

analysis Figure 2. Model I path

The influence of teacher job satisfaction (X1), teacher guidance (X2) Discipline (Z)

satisfaction on Class

e1 shows the amount of variance in the compensation variable that is not explained by the variables Teacher Job Satisfaction, Teacher Guidance, Class Discipline.

Rumus : $e1 : \sqrt{1 - R^2}$

Table 3. Regresi Model I Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8,424	1,656		5,087	,000
	Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1)	,309	,138	,249	2,235	,028
	Teacher Guidance (X2)	,194	,094	,231	2,078	,040

a. Dependent Variable: Class Discipline (Z)

The SPSS output results in table 3. with a Village Fund Standardized Coefficients value in equation I of 0.249 and a significant value of 0.028, which is smaller than 0.05, shows that teacher job satisfaction has an effect on classroom discipline. The value 0.249 is the path value (p1) and the SPSS output results with the standardized Coefficients Beta B value for teacher guidance in equation 1 are 0.231 and are significant at 0.04, which is smaller than 0.05, indicating that teacher guidance has an effect on classroom discipline. The value 0.231 is the path value (p2).

The results of the path analysis of regression equation 1 are as presented in table 3, so it can be seen that the regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = 8.242 + 0.249 X1 + 0.231 X2 + e1$$

It can be seen from the regression equation that the constant value of 8.242 indicates that if the Teacher Job Satisfaction variable is considered constant, then the average Learning Achievement (Y) is 8.242. The regression coefficient for Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) of

0.249 states that if teacher Job Satisfaction increases by one unit it will increase Learning Achievement by 0.249 and from the regression equation it can also be seen that, a constant value of 8.242 indicates that if the Teacher Guidance variable is considered constant, then the average -The average student learning achievement (Y) is 8.242. The Teacher Guidance regression coefficient (X2) of 0.231 states that if Teacher Guidance increases by one unit it will increase Class Discipline by 0.231.

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

Model II Path regression analysis

Path analysis is only used to determine the pattern of relationships between three or more variables. The following shows the second path

Analysis model: Figure 3. Regression model II

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1), Teacher Guidance (X2), Class Discipline (Z) on Student Learning Achievement (Y)

e2 shows the amount of variance in the Student Learning Achievement variable that is not explained by the variables Teacher Job Satisfaction, Teacher Guidance and Class Discipline

$$\text{Rumus : } e2 : \sqrt{1 - R^2}$$

Tabel 4. Regresi Model II

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7,163	1,704		4,204	,000
	Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1)	,421	,130	,324	3,251	,002
	Teacher Guidance (X2)	,227	,087	,258	2,595	,011
	Class Discipline (Z)	,193	,093	,184	2,079	,040

a. Dependent Variable: Student Learning Achievement (Y)

The output results of table 4 with the Standardized Coefficients Beta value for Teacher Job Satisfaction in equation 2 are 0.324 and are significant at 0.002, which is smaller than 0.05, indicating that teacher Job Satisfaction has an effect on student learning achievement. The value 0.324 is the path value (p4). The SPSS output results with the Standardized Coefficients Beta Teacher Guidance value and equation 2 are 0.258 and are significant at 0.011, which is smaller than 0.05, indicating that teacher guidance has an effect on student learning achievement. The value 0.258 is the path value (p5). The SPSS output results with the Standardized Coefficients Beta Class Discipline value in equation 2 are 0.184 and are significant at 0.040, which is smaller than 0.05, indicating that Class Discipline (Z) has an effect on Student Learning Achievement (Y). The value 0.184 is the path value (p6).

The results of the path analysis of regression equation 2 are as presented in table 5.17, so it can be seen that the regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = 7.163 + 0.324 X1 + 0.258 X2 + 0.184 Z + e2$$

It can be seen from the regression equation that the constant value of 7.163 indicates that if the teacher job satisfaction variable is considered constant, then the average student learning achievement (Y) is 7.163. The regression coefficient for Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) of 0.324 states that if Teacher Job Satisfaction increases by one unit it will increase Student Learning Achievement by 0.324. It can be seen from the regression equation that the constant value of 7.163 indicates that if the Teacher Guidance variable (X2) is considered constant, then the average Student Learning Achievement (Y) is 7.163. The regression coefficient for Teacher Guidance (X2) of 0.258 states that if Teacher Guidance (X2) increases by one unit it will increase student learning achievement by 0.258. From the regression equation, it can be seen that, the constant value of 7.163 indicates that if the Class Discipline (Z) variable is 0.184, it means that if Class Discipline (Z) increases by one unit, it will increase student learning achievement by 0.184.

Sobel Test

Based on the results of data processing using regression, the regression results will be presented which can be described as follows:

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

Equation 1 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8,424	1,656		5,087	,000
	Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1)	,309	,138	,249	2,235	,028
	Teacher Guidance (X2)	,194	,094	,231	2,078	,040

a. Dependent Variable: Class Discipline (Z)

Equation 2 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7,163	1,704		4,204	,000
	Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1)	,421	,130	,324	3,251	,002
	Teacher Guidance (X2)	,227	,087	,258	2,595	,011
	Class Discipline (Z)	,193	,093	,184	2,079	,040

a. Dependent Variable: Student Learning Achievement (Y)

The model above is a model formed from the results of the first and second regressions to form a path analysis model with the Class Discipline variable as the mediator. The z value from the Sobel test cannot be generated directly from the regression results but by manual calculation using the Sobel test formula. The results of calculating the z value from the Sobel test are: Sobel Test Results: Teacher Job Satisfaction on Student Learning Achievement through Classroom Discipline Please enter the necessary parameter values, and then click 'Calculate'.

Sobel test statistic: 1.52207275
 One-tailed probability: 0.06399543
 Two-tailed probability: 0.12799085

From the results of the Sobel test calculation, the calculated t value was 1.522 < t table 1.982 with a significance level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that there is no influence of teacher job satisfaction on student learning achievement through the mediation of

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

Class Discipline as an intervening variable.

Figure. Equation 11

Please enter the necessary parameter values, and then click 'Calculate'.

A: 0.194
 B: 0.193
 SE_A: 0.094
 SE_B: 0.093
 Sobel test statistic: 1.46337558
 One-tailed probability: 0.07168232
 Two-tailed probability: 0.14336464

From the results of the Sobel test calculation, the calculated t value was $1.463 < t_{table} 1.982$ with a significance level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that there is no influence of Teacher Guidance on Student Learning Achievement through the mediation of Class Discipline as an intervening variable

Uji Koefisien Determinan Hasil Output SPSS:

Table 5 the coefficient of determination Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.617 ^a	.681	.361	1,81378	1,929

Predictors: (Constant), Class Discipline (Z), Teacher Guidance (X2), Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1)

Dependent Variable: Student Learning Achievement (Y)

In table 5, the coefficient of determination (R-square) is a value (proportion) that measures the ability of the independent variables (X) used in the regression equation to explain variations in the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination value ranges from 0 to 1. From the table above, it is known that the coefficient of determination (R- square) is 0.68.1. This value can explain that X1, and the remaining 21.5% is influenced by other factors outside the regression model used.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) on Student Learning Achievement (Y) UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

There is an influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) on Student Learning Achievement where the probability value of X1 is

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

0.002. This value is smaller than 0.05 or the calculated t value is $3,125 > t$ table 1,984 ($n-1 = 100-1$ alpha 5%) so it can be concluded that the Teacher Job Satisfaction variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the student learning achievement variable (Y) at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Istu Hardjana, 2018 Teacher Job Satisfaction in Improving Student Learning Achievement at Ngemplak 3 Kwadungan Elementary School, Widodomartani, Ngemplak, Sleman 2016/2017 Academic Year. The aspects discussed are the principal's leadership style in improving student learning achievement, the principal's strategy in improving student learning achievement, and the obstacles faced by school principals in improving student learning achievement. Also in line with Sinambela's theory (2012: 260), which states that employees who have high job satisfaction will 1) believe that in the work process, the organization will provide satisfaction; 2) care about the quality of their work; 3) more attached to the organization; 4) has high speed; 5) more productive. Thus, teachers who have high job satisfaction can be more productive than teachers who have low job satisfaction.

2. The Influence of Teacher Guidance (X2) on Student Learning Achievement (Y) UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

There is an influence of teacher guidance (X2) on student learning achievement (Y), where the probability value of X2 is 0.040. This value is smaller than 0.05 or the t value is

$2,595 > t$ table 1,984 ($n-1 = 100-1$ alpha 5 %) %) so it can be concluded that the Teacher Guidance variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the student learning achievement variable (Y) at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

The results of this research are in line with Bayu Umbara's 2008 research "The Influence of Guidance Teachers on Increasing Students' Islamic Religious Education Learning Achievement at SMPN 13 Depok." 13 Depok is 0.73 and this correlation is classified as strong or high. Abin Syamsuddin (2003) states that teachers as supervisors are required to be able to identify students who are suspected of having learning difficulties, carry out diagnoses and prognoses, and if it is still within the limits of their authority, must help solve them (remedial teaching). This assignment will have an impact on increasing student learning achievement.

3. The Influence of Class Discipline (Z) on Student Learning Achievement (Y) of UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

There is an influence of class discipline (Z) on student learning achievement (Y)

where the probability value of Z is 0.026. This value is smaller than 0.05 or the t value is $2,079 > t$ table 1.984 ($n-1 = 100-1$ alpha 5 %) %) so it can be concluded that the Class Discipline (Z) variable has a positive and significant effect on the student learning achievement variable. (Y) at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City In learning, discipline is very necessary because discipline gives birth to a spirit of appreciating time, not wasting time passing by in emptiness (Djamarah, 2002:67). Learning discipline in the classroom is an attitude that is formed through a process of a series of behaviors that show individual values, obedience and provisions based on individual moral values to obtain changes in behavior that include changes in thinking, attitudes and actions that are in accordance with established rules and regulations. someone who studies consistently and consistently in an effort to achieve learning achievement.

4. Influence of teacher job satisfaction (X1). Simultaneous Teacher Guidance (X2) and Class Discipline (Z) on the Learning Achievement of UPT SPF Village Students at Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

There is an influence on teacher job satisfaction (X1). Teacher Guidance (X2) and Class Discipline (Z) simultaneously on the Learning Achievement of UPT SPF State Middle School Students in Rappocini District, Makassar City. The simultaneous test shows that there is a significant influence between the independent variable (X) simultaneously on the dependent variable (Y). can be seen in the table above, namely with the sig value. F test of 0.000 at a significance level of 0.05. This value is smaller than 0.05, which indicates that all independent variables together have an influence on Student Learning Achievement (Y). at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City Of the three variables based on theory and previous research, as stated above, the variable teacher job satisfaction on student learning achievement. With teacher job satisfaction, teachers will be more productive in teaching, care about the quality of teaching, be more disciplined and have a passion for teaching which of course has an impact on achievement. student learning.. Variations in Teacher Guidance. The teacher's job as a guide is required to be able to identify students who are suspected of experiencing difficulties in learning, carry out diagnoses, prognoses, learning difficulties must help solve student learning problems (remedial teaching). Based on this theory, it is very appropriate for the teacher's task Guiding will be able to improve student learning achievement. Classroom discipline variables are something related to a person's self-control to be obedient to the forms of rules that have been set in the class in order to achieve the desired goals, including learning objectives (learning achievement).

The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

5. Effect of Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) on Student Learning Achievement (Y) Through Class Discipline (Z) UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City There is no influence of teacher job satisfaction (X1) on student learning achievement (Y) through class discipline (Z). at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.

From the results of the Sobel test calculation, the calculated t value was $1.522 < t$ table 1.982 with a significance level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that there is no influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction on student learning achievement through the mediation of Class Discipline as an intervening variable. Chamundeswari's 2013 research showed that the teachers studied had good job satisfaction and performance because the teachers enjoyed better infrastructure facilities and a pleasant working environment. So from Chamundeswari's research work performance can be influenced by job satisfaction and teacher performance. According to Tella, Ayeni, and Popoola (2007:5) teachers' work performance is influenced by their teaching satisfaction, while dissatisfaction will influence and cause lethargy or lack of motivation at work and impact on low organizational commitment. Teachers who are less satisfied with their work duties will be less responsible and will ultimately leave the job. When teacher job satisfaction is not met, such as not enjoying better infrastructure facilities and an unpleasant work environment, it will affect student performance and learning achievement, so there is teacher job dissatisfaction at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.

6. The Effect of Teacher Guidance (X1) on Student Learning Achievement (Y) Through Class Discipline (Z) UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

There is no influence of teacher guidance (X1) on student learning achievement (Y) through class discipline (Z). at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City. From the results of the Sobel test calculations, the calculated t value was $1.463 < t$ table 1.982 with a significance level of 0.05. So it can be concluded that there is no influence of Teacher Guidance on student learning achievement through the mediation of Class Discipline as an intervening variable. Teachers who are less satisfied with their work duties will be less responsible and will ultimately leave the job. When teacher job satisfaction is not met, such as not enjoying better infrastructure facilities and an unpleasant work environment, this will affect performance, including in guiding students. teachers at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City. So it is recommended that schools, especially school principals, pay attention to teacher job satisfaction because it influences the process of guiding students at school.

CONCLUSION

1. Teacher Job Satisfaction (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the Student Learning Achievement variable (Y) at UPT SPF public junior high schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.
2. Teacher Guidance (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the Student Learning Achievement variable (Y) at UPT SPF public junior high schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.
3. Class Discipline (Z) has a positive and significant effect on the Student Learning Achievement variable (Y) at UPT SPF public junior high schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City.
4. There is an influence on teacher job satisfaction (X1). Teacher Guidance (X2) and Class Discipline (Z) simultaneously on the Learning Achievement of State Middle School UPT SPF Students in Rappocini District, Makassar City
5. There is no influence of teacher job satisfaction (X1) on student learning achievement (Y) through class discipline (Z). at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City
6. There is no influence of teacher guidance (X1) on student learning achievement (Y) through class discipline (Z). at UPT SPF State Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

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The Influence of Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Guidance on Student Achievement Through Class Discipline at UPT SPF of Public Middle Schools in Rappocini District, Makassar City

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